

APPLICATION OF GAMING TECHNOLOGIES IN LOGOPEDIC TRAINING

Rimbayeva Ozoda Bazarbayevna

Student of the Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12730382>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th July 2024

Accepted: 11th July 2024

Online: 12th July 2024

KEYWORDS

Game, training, technology, interactive games, individual approach, computer games, programs.

ABSTRACT

Logopedic training plays an important role in correcting speech disorders in children and supporting speech development. The use of Game technologies in these activities helps to increase the interest of children and increase the effectiveness of training. In this article, we will talk about the advantages and methods of using game technologies in logopedic training.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИГРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ЛОГОПЕДИЧЕСКОМ ОБУЧЕНИИ

Римбаева Озода Базарбаевна

Студентка Нукусского государственного педагогического института

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12730382>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th July 2024

Accepted: 11th July 2024

Online: 12th July 2024

KEYWORDS

Игра, обучение, технология, интерактивные игры, индивидуальный подход, компьютерные игры, Программы.

ABSTRACT

Логопедические занятия играют важную роль в коррекции речевых нарушений у детей и поддержке речевого развития. Применение игровых технологий в этих занятиях способствует повышению интереса детей и повышению эффективности занятий. В этой статье мы расскажем о преимуществах и методах применения игровых технологий в логопедической деятельности.

Advantages of using gaming technologies in logopedic training:

Motivation and interest for children: Games attract the attention of children and make training fun for them. This increases the activity of children and forms a positive attitude towards training. One of the activities of childhood is gaming activities.

Reducing stress in children: Games improve children's mental state and reduce stress. This, in turn, helps children to be free and natural in the process of speech therapy. By adding

different games to the workout, we can easily make different tasks for the child and form the idea of playing games in the process, and not doing tasks for the child.

Interactive learning: game technologies allow children to learn in an interactive way. This will help develop the children's speech apparatus. By incorporating many of the exercises you need for training into your game activities, we can easily deliver these to the child, as well as increase our ability to do them easily.

Individual approach: it is easier to provide an individual approach to each child through games. It is possible to organize classes in accordance with the abilities and needs of children. Choosing toys with different themes, we give them to the child. The child, on the other hand, sorts out toys from among them, which are related to the sphere in which he is interested. Through this we will be able to identify the subject of interest in it and we will be able to take advantage of it in our next training.

METHODS OF APPLICATION OF GAMING TECHNOLOGIES

Computer games and applications. Computer games and mobile applications are very effective tools for logopedic training. Below are some popular apps and their benefits:

Speech Blubs: children learn to pronounce sounds correctly, and this process is carried out in an interesting way.

Articulation Station: this app helps children perform articulation exercises and develop pronunciation skills.

Endless Alphabet: is a game for children to learn letters and words through which speech and vocabulary can be enhanced.

Splingo: this application helps to learn grammatical rules and increases the interest of children through interactive games.

Interactive Whiteboards. Interactive whiteboards (smartboards) are a very effective tool for logopedic training. Through them, it is possible to work interactively with children, complete various tasks and conduct Games. With interactive whiteboards, the following activities can be carried out:

Vocalization exercises: through an interactive whiteboard, children perform exercises to distinguish sounds and pronounce them correctly.

Increase vocabulary: the Board plays the correct placement of words and their conjugation.

Grammar exercises: through an interactive whiteboard, children perform exercises to learn and apply grammatical rules.

Paper and board games. Paper and board games are widely used in logopedic training. Through these games, children can correctly pronounce sounds, increase vocabulary and learn grammatical rules:

Bingo: through the game of Bingo, children learn to distinguish sounds and pronounce them correctly.

Memory: memory games help to increase children's vocabulary and learn new words.

Through the game Scrabble: Scrabble, children develop the ability to compose words and apply grammatical rules.

Role-Playing Games. Role-playing games play an important role in developing children's communication skills. Through these games, children learn to apply speech in a natural state, fulfilling various roles:

Store GAME: children play the role of sellers and buyers in the store, using different words and sentences in the process of trading.

Restaurant Game: children, playing in the role of waiters and customers, develop speech skills in the process of ordering and receiving.

Professional games: by performing different professions, children learn new words and develop communication skills.

Game activist is considered one of the main activities of preschool and small school-age children. Through this, we can establish free communication with the child, adapt the child to ourselves, identify his interests and abilities, have the opportunity to learn about his hidden characteristics and what he comes into contact with the environment through.

Not only in logopedic training is the game activity a non-complex process that a parent at home can also use in the process of dealing with their child. Through the activity of play, the worldview, thinking, attention, speech, phonemic hearing and imagination of the child are formed and developed. Through gaming activities, we can again check the child, determine the indicators of his development. That is, observing the child's play activity, we can learn, control the accuracy of his actions, speed, purposefulness, the degree of concentration or dispersion of his attention, the degree of development of auditory perception and the various features of the development of the head through the activities of the game.

According to the many effectiveness characteristics of the game activist, we will be able to apply it not only in speech therapy, but also in general and specialized school classes, as a type of developmental activity in various other activities.

The targeted use of a game activist can develop characteristics in a child such as combativity, teamwork, aspiration, curiosity and mobility, subsequently forming skills to apply them throughout their lives.

The use of gaming technologies in logopedic training increases the interest of children and makes training effective. Computer games, interactive whiteboards, paper and board games, and role-playing methods have a positive effect on children's speech development. Therefore, logopeds should widely use gaming technologies in their work and organize fun and useful activities for children.

References:

1. Logopedia-M.Ayupova. Tashkent-2019
2. Fundamentals of defectology-V.S.Rachmanova. Tashkent "NISO polygraph" 2017
3. <https://openidea.uz>
4. <https://interonconf.org>
5. <https://lib.cspi.uz>